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**WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF SUBMITTING A PREPRINT
ARTICLE TO BIORXIV AND CHEMRXIV: ARE BIORXIV
AND CHEMRXIV ACTING AS MOB PEER REVIEW
CENSORSHIP BOARD?**

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Abstract.

According to their websites of bioRxiv and chemRxiv do not perform peer reviews of preprint articles that are submitted to them and that they only screen submitted preprint articles for . The experience of this author is that bioRxiv and chemRxiv not only perform extensive reviews of submitted preprint articles, they also act a Mob Peer Review Censorship Board. The qualifications of the Mob Peer Reviewers of bioRxiv and chemRxiv are questionable. It is impossible to contact the persons who run bioRxiv and chemRxiv. It is quite disturbing and disgusting that the flow of scientific information in the "freest country of the world" is controlled by two outfits that acts as Mob Peer Review Censorship Board. The actions of bioRxiv and chemRxiv which operate with tax paper's largesse are selective, opaque, arbitrary and a violations of Fundamental Right of the United States citizens to write and publish.

bioRxiv [1] advertises in its website that (i) "it is a free online archive and distribution service for unpublished preprints in the life sciences", (ii) "It is operated by Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, a not-for-profit research and educational institution", (iii) "By posting preprints on bioRxiv, authors are able to make their findings immediately available to the scientific community and receive feedback on draft manuscripts before they are submitted to journals", (iv) "Articles are not peer-reviewed, edited, or typeset before being posted online" and (v) However, all articles undergo a basic screening process for offensive and/or non-scientific content and for material that might pose a health or biosecurity risk and are checked for plagiarism. ChemRxiv [2] advertises in its website that (i) "it is a free submission, distribution, and archive service for unpublished preprints in chemistry and related areas", (ii) it gives "researchers across a broad range of fields related to the chemical sciences the opportunity to share early results with colleagues and receive recommendations for improvement, ahead of formal peer review and publication", (iii) "researchers can use it to "gather feedback and context from fellow scientists, establish the priority and precedence of a discovery, find potential collaborators and rapidly disseminate work to a wide audience, make research work more discoverable, document research results for grant reviewers in advance of publication, facilitate rapid evaluation of results, spot trends and encourage a broad range of constructive feedback, and (iv) it "conducts a basic screening for plagiarism, offensive language, non-scientific, and inappropriate content, and we will exclude materials that may pose a health or security risk if identified. Beyond this screening, the files are unedited and are not peer reviewed.

At first glance, the above advertisements of bioRxiv and ChemRxiv are quite laudable and appear quite altruistic for the research community at large. Most Scientific Researchers have adopted the concept of preprint submission as part of an obligatory exercise (another hoop to jump over in the un-ending obstacles that Scientific Researchers who work with their brains and hands in the laboratory have to climb over nowadays) in the business of doing research. Many have argued that the regular way of getting one's scientific work published through a system of peer review process (whether the current system of peer review process is honest or dishonest is another debate) takes too long. Are bioRxiv and ChemRxiv being honest about their activities, and are they performing with complete

openness, transparency, fairness and due process which characterize not only the American system jurisprudence but also all-American endeavors. In the United States of America, we like to think that when there is a process of selection in all aspect of life in America, the process of selection is supposed to open, transparent, fair and pursuant to certain rules and regulation. The process of selecting preprint articles to be published in bioRxiv and ChemRxiv should in principle be quite straight forward and not generate any debate or controversy. After all, both bioRxiv and ChemRxiv advertise in their websites that they do not conduct "peer review" (whatever it means!) and that they only conduct "a basic screening process for offensive and/or non-scientific content and for material that might pose a health or biosecurity risk and are checked for plagiarism" or "conduct a basic screening for plagiarism, offensive language, non-scientific, and inappropriate content, and we will exclude materials that may pose a health or security risk if identified" [1,2].

Based on the above understanding, the author of this report submitted a number of preprint articles to bioRxiv and ChemRxiv, obligatory steps nowadays as they tend to provide certain benefits, including (as ChemRxiv put it): the following: "researchers can use it to "gather feedback and context from fellow scientists, establish the priority and precedence of a discovery, find potential collaborators and rapidly disseminate work to a wide audience, make research work more discoverable, document research results for grant reviewers in advance of publication, facilitate rapid evaluation of results, spot trends and encourage a broad range of constructive feedback. To my surprise and disgust, several of my preprint articles were rejected by bioRxiv and ChemRxiv for unscientific, derogatory, mean and what can be termed as "pin-head" reasons. One preprint article that I submitted to bioRxiv was entitled "**INHIBITION OF THE DIMERIZATION OF SARS-COV-2 ENCODED NUCLEOCAPSID PROTEIN BY CHLOROPHYLL A, HALOTHANE AND TETRAETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOOCTYL ETHER**". It took me and my student more than 90 days, sometimes working until 5 a.m in the morning, to finish the work described in the preprint article. The reason bioRxiv gave for rejecting my preprint was: "We regret to inform you that your manuscript is inappropriate for bioRxiv. As an abundance of caution, bioRxiv is not currently posting predictions of drug/therapeutic efficacy/potential for treatment of COVID-19 that are based solely on in silico work, given concerns about drug availability and dangers to the general public. This manuscript should

instead undergo rapid peer review at a journal before dissemination. This has been a difficult decision not arrived at lightly and we understand it may be disappointing, but we currently feel this is the most responsible course of action in these exceptional circumstances". The letter of rejection was signed by an anonymous nobody. Another preprint article that I submitted to bioRxiv was entitled "**MUTATIONS IN THE SPIKE PROTEIN OF SARS-COV-2 VARIANT, B.1.526 OCCUR AT TWO PHOSPHORYLATION SITES: EFFECTS ON STABILITY AND BINDING TO ACE2 AND DC-SIGN.**". The reason bioRxiv gave for rejecting my preprint was: "We regret to inform you that your manuscript is inappropriate for bioRxiv. As bioRxiv is intended for dissemination of research articles containing new data, rather than other types of content, it was determined that this manuscript would be more appropriately distributed after peer review rather than through bioRxiv". Again the letter of rejection was signed by an anonymous nobody.

The tone of the rejection letters from bioRxiv was not only condescending but also unscientific and quite derogatory. Although, bioRxiv advertises in its website that it does not conduct "peer review" of submitted preprint articles, it is clear to any person of average intelligence that bioRxiv has been performing "reviews" of my pre-print papers. bioRxiv did not just perform a "basic screening process for offensive and/or non-scientific content and for material that might pose a health or biosecurity risk and are checked for plagiarism", it also determined whether the scientific content of my pre-print paper was up to certain standard scientifically and whether the scientific content of my pre-print was new or not. The author of this report challenges the "nobody" from bioRxiv and also bioRxiv to prove that my pre-prints had any offensive language, non-scientific content, or contain description of any material that might pose a health or biosecurity risk, or contain any plagiarized material. It is clear that the "nobody" from bioRxiv is a crass imbecile who has no idea what the discipline of life sciences constitute of and how scientific discoveries in the life sciences are made and described. It is not clear what scientific qualifications the "nobody" from bioRxiv have to allow himself/herself to review the scientific merit of my preprint article. the "nobody" from bioRxiv and bioRxiv should certainly know that it takes many years to develop a successful drug that target the dimerization and oligomerization of

SARS-COV-2 encoded Nucleocapsid protein (NCp). However, considering that that the whole country is an emergency pandemic situation, surely, the Scientific Researchers who are spending day and night toiling in the laboratory working with their brains and hands would be interested to learn about potential life-saving measures which they could in principle test themselves (It is a gift to humanity). Acting as a Mob Censorship Board on account of an "abundance of caution" is not only unscientific but also pure arrogance. Whom the nobody from bioRxiv and bioRxiv are trying to protect? bioRxiv has published incendiary, unscientific, derogatory, racist and xenophobic preprint articles, including preprint article of Bloom, J.D. [3] in which he insinuates that the Chinese Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology had hidden early sequences of SARS-COV-2 when it is well documented that the data that Bloom, J.D. claimed was being intentionally hidden was published and can be accessed by anybody. The author of this Report would like to know if bioRxiv has any hidden agenda by acting as Mob Censorship Review Board. Inciting ridicule, hatred and violence on false unscientific innuendos appear to be cautioned and propagated by bioRxiv. Is bioRxiv following the steps of the founder of Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory who was a racist, xenophobic, anti-semitic and misogynist thief (Watson and Crick stole the work of Rosalind Franklin and derided her because she was Jewish and a woman). Where is the transparency, fairness and due process that bioRxiv is supposed to exercise as an entity that is supported by Tax payer's largesse (It would be interesting what the Chan Zuckerberg Foundation thinks of how its contribution is being spent).

If the author of this Report wanted his preprint articles to be reviewed as they do in a scientific journal that has a proper system of peer review process, he would have sent elsewhere. To have my preprint articles reviewed by a "nobody" with questionable scientific qualifications from bioRxiv is not only an insult but a violation of the tradition of openness, transparency, fairness and due process that characterize the very foundation of modern science.

The title of the pre-print article that the author of this report submitted to ChemRxiv was **"MUTATIONS OF PHOSPHORYLATION SITES IN SARS-COV-2 ENCODED**

NUCLEOCAPSID PROTEIN ENHANCE ITS DIMERIZATION". The said preprint article was rejected by an individual named M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. on the following ground: "I am declining your submission because it appears to contain quite a lot of reused text and language from your previous works published in BioRxiv and in the Scientific Journal of Biology. Given that the reuse extends beyond simple turn-of-phrase, we need to classify this as self-plagiarism and therefore cannot consider it further. Moreover, the work itself appears to be not chemical in nature, and so I believe that ChemRxiv is not the most appropriate venue". That person named M, Yavanthi, Ph.D. is a crass imbecile who has no idea what chemical science is an understatement.. Any person of average intelligence will know that a preprint article entitled "**MUTATIONS OF PHOSPHORYLATION SITES IN SARS-COV-2 ENCODED NUCLEOCAPSID PROTEIN ENHANCE ITS DIMERIZATION**" has everything to do with chemistry. That the individual named M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. does not know anything about the role of protein phosphorylation in the control of cellular activity, including protein-protein interactions who underlie most if not all cellular processes is beyond normal comprehension. That the individual named Yavanthi, Ph.D. with the backing of ChemRxiv and ChemRxiv would actually state that it is not clear whether a paper entitled "**MUTATIONS OF PHOSPHORYLATION SITES IN SARS-COV-2 ENCODED NUCLEOCAPSID PROTEIN ENHANCE ITS DIMERIZATION**" "appears to be not chemical in nature provides further evidence that the individual M, Yavanthi, Ph.D. is the worst crass imbecile that the author of this Report has ever encountered (The author of this Report has encountered many stupid so-called Scientific Researchers who do not work whit their brains and hands at the bench in the laboratory but claim to be experts and pundits). The insinuation that the author of this Report has practiced self-plagiarism is unscientific, derogatory and defamatory. First the imbecilic M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. and ChemRxiv must define what self-plagiarism scientifically. The term self-plagiarism is oxymoronic and can only come from a crass imbecile.

According to any dictionary that one can consult free of charge on the internet, plagiarism is defined as "the practice of taking someone else's work or ideas and passing them off as one's own". In other words, plagiarism has occurred one steals from someone else. Legally,

one cannot steal from oneself. Nevertheless, the moronic Mob Review Censorship Board represented by the imbecilic individual named M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. and ChemRxiv and many others has come up with the oxymoronic term of self-plagiarism. A more appropriate term that is less caustic and derogatory can be termed "reusism" because in the scientific world, one is in fact dealing with the re-use of texts, sentences, description of methods and procedures, description of ideas, theories, hypotheses, conclusions, principles, rules and laws. How else can one describe Newton's Laws of Motions if not by reusing the writings of Isaac Newton. How else can one describe Einstein's theory of relativity with respect to the equation $E = MC^2$ if not by reusing Einstein famous equation. Nowadays, no one could be accused of plagiarism if one uses the equation $E = MC^2$ without referencing Albert Einstein famous paper. Anyone who claims ownership or the father of $E = MC^2$ would be laughed at as a crass imbecile. Reusing one's description of ideas, theories, hypotheses and conclusions is scientific and permissible. It cannot be termed a form of plagiarism because legally one cannot steal from oneself, especially if one has referenced the use in question. Indeed, recently, it is recognized that "Text recycling is common if not ubiquitous in the sciences" and some scientific journals allow authors to use text that is identical or substantively equivalent to prior publications as long as they cite the original source " [4,5]. It is not clear where M. Yavanthi got his/her doctorate degree. Imbecilic individual like M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. most probably did not get to study the History and Philosophy of Science (The study of the History and Philosophy of Science is not a requirement in most Graduate Schools in the United States of America and elsewhere. It is also known that not all Ph.D. degrees are equivalent and not all Graduate Schools are qualified to grant Ph.D. degrees). Imbecilic individual like M. Yavanthi, Ph.D. must go back to school to read and study the History and Philosophy of Science, and Karl Popper's Logic of Scientific Discovery, Thomas Kuhn, Theory of Scientific Revolutions and Paul Feyerabend's Against Method.

Both bioRxiv and ChemRxiv are supported by tax payers' largesse which means that they are operating with the approval of the Internal Revenue Service which regulates entities like bioRxiv and ChemRxiv. Pursuant to the laws of this country, Organizations that are Not for Profit entities and are supported by Tax Payer's largesse like bioRxiv and ChemRxiv "are supposed to operate for public benefit, must operate under the principles

of accountability, trustworthiness, honesty, and openness, must adopt, establish and regularly review their mission statements to explain their purposes, and must report any significant changes to the IRS". Do bioRxiv and ChemRxiv operate for public benefit under the principles of accountability, trustworthiness, honesty, and openness, The above examples show clearly that the benefits of bioRxiv and ChemRxiv to the general are questionable as (i) they are doing badly what is already being done by scientific journals that have established well-organized system of peer review, (ii) their operations are opaque (the author of this Report has tried to contact the owners and advisors of bioRxiv and ChemRxiv without success), (iii) they are performing "Mob Peer Review" of submitted preprint articles even though on their websites, they claim that they do not conduct "peer review", (iii) through their Mob Review Censorship Board, they have adopted political agendas that aim to censor preprint scientific articles that espouse different point of views. bioRxiv and ChemRxiv have conflict of interest that they must declare to the IRS, their contributors and users (What is the exact relationship between bioRxiv and Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, and ChemRxiv and Cambridge University Press.

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Authorship and publication matters: credit and credibility.